

Trinuclear Ru^{III}-Mn^{II}-Ru^{III} complexes incorporating azo-oxime function

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Abstract : Oximate-bridged trinuclear Ru^{III}-Mn^{II}-Ru^{III} complexes have been synthesized by "complex as a ligand" strategy. They are characterized by spectroscopic methods, cyclic voltammetric techniques as well as by X-ray crystallography. Such examples of trinuclear species incorporating second row transition metal ions are rare.

Keyword : Oximate-bridged polynucleation.

Introduction

Polynuclear metal complexes are of considerable interest in connection with spin exchange and charge transfer¹⁻⁸ between the metal ions via the bridging ligands. They are also of potential use as models to mimic the active site structures of certain metalloproteins and metallozymes^{9,10}. Another utility of these complexes is in designing new magnetic materials such as new molecular based magnets¹¹.

Oximate-bridged polynucleation has been known for quite sometime¹² and there are several reports of such structurally characterized species¹³⁻²¹, but in most of the cases the ions used are of the first row transition series. The heavier ions occur in a few scattered examples²²⁻²⁶. In the present work, we have explored the synthetic strategy of the trinuclear complexes of type [Ru^{III}Cl₂L₂]Mn^{II}(H₂O)₂, **3**, where L is arylazooximes of type **2**. The peculiar structural characteristic of the complexes is also revealed in this work and these are one of the rare examples of oximate-bridged polynuclear species incorporating trivalent ruthenium.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

The strategy employed to design the synthesis of the trinuclear species is the 'complex as ligand' approach i.e.

using a mononuclear complex which has certain potential donor centres to bind to another metal ion. In the present work the 'complex as ligand' is *trans*-[Ru^{III}Cl₂(HL)L], **1**²⁷, which when deprotonated, behaves as a bidentate uni-negative ligand to bind to a second metal ion. An alcoholic solution of the deprotonated mononuclear Ru^{III} complex, **1** (2 equivalents), when treated with Mn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (1 equivalents) forms dark purple coloured trinuclear complexes of type **3** in excellent yields.

The complexes of type **3**, exhibit a few characteristic bands in the visible region and a low energy band at around 1000 nm, the latter is probably due to ligand (π) → metal (t_{2g}) charge transfer (LMCT)²⁸. A single sharp IR stretch at ~350 cm⁻¹ is obtained and it is attributed to *trans* disposition of the Ru-Cl bonds. They are electroactive (Table 1) and display two quasi-reversible cyclic voltammetric responses in the region of ~0.20 and 0.40 V, which are assigned to the Ru^{III}/Ru^{II} reductions of the two ruthenium(III) centre in the trinuclear complexes²⁰. The magnetic moment of the complexes are somewhat lower than expected, even at room temperature. This must be due to the presence of the oximate-bridge between Ru^{III} and Mn^{II}, which are extremely efficient in mediating strong anti-ferromagnetic interaction, via an orbital exchange pathway, essentially of σ-nature^{15-18,21}. The magnetic studies in the form of variable temperature magnetic moment and EPR will be reported elsewhere.

Table 1. Spectral and electrochemical^a data for [Ru^{III}Cl₂L₂]₂Mn(H₂O)₂

Complex	UV-Vis data λ_{max} , nm (log ϵ , M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	IR data $\nu_{\text{Ru-Cl}}$ (cm ⁻¹)	$E_{1/2}^b$, V (ΔE_p^c , mV)
[RuCl ₂ (PhL ¹) ₂] ₂ Mn(H ₂ O) ₂	1010 (3.682) 560 (4.497) 525 ^d (4.463) 370 (4.739)	350	0.38 (100), 0.13 (90)
[RuCl ₂ (PhL ²) ₂] ₂ Mn(H ₂ O) ₂	1015 (3.724) 555 (4.395) 530 ^d (4.372) 375 (4.523)	360	0.40 (85), 0.15 (95)

^aIn acetonitrile solution.

^b $E_{1/2}$ is calculated as the average of anodic (E_{pa}) and cathodic (E_{pc}) peak potentials.

^c $\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$.

^dShoulder.

Structure :

Crystal data for the studied compound are presented in Table 2. The crystal structure of [Ru^{III}Cl₂L₂]₂Mn^{II}(H₂O)₂ has been determined in the form of water-dichloromethane adduct, [Ru^{III}Cl₂L₂]₂Mn^{II}(H₂O)₂.H₂O.CH₂Cl₂. The lat-

tice consist of two metrically similar but crystallographically distinct centro-symmetric trinuclear molecules (Molecule 1 and Molecule 2) each of composition [Ru^{III}Cl₂L₂]₂Mn^{II}(H₂O)₂. A view of molecule 1 is depicted in Fig. 1 and selected bond parameters for both the

Table 2. Technical details of data acquisition and selected refinement results for **3**

Compound	[RuCl ₂ L ¹] ₂ Mn(H ₂ O) ₂ ·H ₂ O·CH ₂ Cl ₂ , 3
Empirical formula	C ₅₃ H ₄₈ Cl ₆ MnN ₁₂ O ₇ Ru ₂
Formula weight	1343.84
Temperature [K]	293
Wavelength	0.71073
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
<i>a</i> [Å]	12.748(11)
<i>b</i> [Å]	15.166(6)
<i>c</i> [Å]	16.069(9)
α [°]	105.79(4)
β [°]	95.25(6)
γ [°]	103.06(5)
Volume [Å ³]	2873(3)
<i>Z</i>	2
μ [mm ⁻¹]	1.007
<i>F</i> (000)	1442
Crystal size [mm ³]	0.44 × 0.38 × 0.14
<i>D</i> _{calcd} (Mg/m ³)	1.553
<i>hkl</i> range	0/13, -16/15, -17/17
2θ range (°)	1.65–22.55
Reflections collected	7458
Reflections unique	7321
Data (<i>F</i> _o > 2σ(<i>F</i> _o))	7296
Parameters	701
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.0441
<i>R</i> 1 [<i>F</i> _o > 2σ(<i>F</i> _o)]	0.0782
<i>WR</i> 2 for all unique data	0.1196
Goodness of fit	1.060

molecules in Table 3. The manganese atom has essentially displaced the oxime proton of the molecules of **1**, making the four oximato-O atoms available for equatorial coordination. The two axial positions of the distorted octahedral geometry are occupied by water molecules.

The Ru–N⁰ (oximato-N) bond lengths [2.004(9) to 2.020(8) Å] are expectedly shorter²⁶ than the Ru–N^a (azo-N) lengths [2.040(8) to 2.054(9)]. The Mn–O lengths in the complex span the interval 2.123(8) to 2.186(9) Å, which is indicative of the high-spin nature of manganese(II)²⁶. The intra-molecular non-bonded Ru(1)⋯Mn(1) distance is 3.998(1) Å and the Ru(2)⋯Mn(2) is 3.997(1) Å. The shortest intermolecular Mn(1)⋯Mn(2) length is 7.972(1) Å. The trinuclear entities are inter-linked through solvent water molecules via hydrogen bonding. In effect the water trimer acts as a bridge between the manganese(II) (Fig. 2), thereby leading to the formation of infinite zig-zag chain incorporating manganese(II) and water molecules.

Conclusion :

The present work demonstrates the synthesis of a rare oximato-bridged trinuclear complexes incorporating trivalent ruthenium along with bivalent manganese. The structure of one of the representative complex reveals that the trinuclear entities are linked to each other through solvent water molecule via H₂O⋯H₂O⋯H₂O hydrogen bonds.

Fig. 1. Perspective view of [Ru^{III}Cl₂L¹]₂Mn^{II}(H₂O)₂·H₂O·CH₂Cl₂

Table 3. Selected bond lengths and angles [Å, °] for [RuCl₂L¹]₂Mn(H₂O)₂·H₂O·CH₂Cl₂, 3

Molecule 1		Molecule 2	
Mn(1)–O(1)	2.134(8)	Mn(2)–O(4)	2.123(8)
Mn(1)–O(2)	2.171(8)	Mn(2)–O(5)	2.124(8)
Mn(1)–O(3)	2.146(9)	Mn(2)–O(6)	2.186(9)
Ru(1)–N(1)	2.040(8)	Ru(2)–N(7)	2.047(9)
Ru(1)–N(3)	2.004(9)	Ru(2)–N(9)	2.040(9)
Ru(1)–N(6)	2.020(8)	Ru(2)–N(12)	2.016(9)
Ru(1)–N(4)	2.054(9)	Ru(2)–N(10)	2.055(9)
Ru(1)–Cl(1)	2.321(3)	Ru(2)–Cl(3)	2.334(3)
Ru(1)–Cl(2)	2.342(3)	Ru(2)–Cl(4)	2.344(3)
N(1)–N(2)	1.287(14)	N(7)–N(8)	1.256(14)
N(3)–O(1)	1.290(11)	N(12)–O(5)	1.269(11)
N(6)–O(2)	1.287(11)	N(9)–O(4)	1.279(11)
O(3)···O(7)	2.785(11)	O(6)···O(7)	2.768(12)
O(2)–Mn(1)–O(3A)	85.7(4)	O(4A)–Mn(2)–O(6)	92.7(4)
O(2)–Mn(1)–O(3)	94.3(4)	O(5)–Mn(2)–O(6)	88.8(4)
O(2A)–Mn(1)–O(1)	92.5(3)	O(5A)–Mn(2)–O(4)	91.3(3)
O(2)–Mn(1)–O(1)	87.5(3)	O(6)–Mn(2)–O(4)	87.3(4)
O(3A)–Mn(1)–O(1)	88.5(4)	O(6A)–Mn(2)–O(4)	92.7(4)
O(3)–Mn(1)–O(1)	91.5(4)	O(5)–Mn(2)–O(4)	89.0(3)
N(3)–Ru(1)–N(6)	100.5(4)	N(9)–Ru(2)–N(12)	100.5(4)
N(6)–Ru(1)–N(4)	75.7(4)	N(9)–Ru(2)–N(10)	175.4(4)
N(3)–Ru(1)–N(1)	75.4(4)	N(9)–Ru(2)–N(7)	75.7(4)
O(1)–N(3)–Ru(1)	126.5(7)	O(4)–N(9)–Ru(2)	126.3(7)
O(2)–N(6)–Ru(1)	115.0(8)	O(5)–N(12)–Ru(2)	126.4(7)
N(4)–Ru(1)–N(1)	108.3(4)	N(12)–Ru(2)–N(10)	75.5(4)
Cl(1)–Ru(1)–Cl(2)	177.39(11)	Cl(3)–Ru(2)–Cl(4)	178.86(11)
O(3)···O(7)···O(6)	134.54(8)	O(7)···O(6)–Mn(2)	112.7(8)

Fig. 2. Hydrogen bonding involving the solvent water molecules.

Experimental

General consideration :

A Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer was used to record the UV-Vis spectra. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured with a model 155 PAR vibrating sample magnetometer fitted with a Walker Scientific L75BAL magnet. Micro-analytical data (C, H, N) were collected by using Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. Electrochemical measurements were performed under nitrogen atmosphere on a PAR 370-4 electrochemistry system using solvents and supporting electrolytes purified/prepared as before²⁹. All potentials are referenced to the standard calomel electrodes.

Synthesis of the complexes :

The ligands HL and the complexes of type *trans*-[RuCl₂(HL)L] were synthesized by reported methods²⁷ while the trinuclear complexes of type [RuCl₂L₂]₂Mn(H₂O)₂ were synthesized by a general method given below.

[RuCl₂L²]₂Mn(H₂O)₂ : 0.2 g (0.32 mmol) of *trans*-[RuCl₂(HL²)L²] was suspended in 15 ml of ethanol and to it 0.013 g (0.33 mmol) of sodium hydroxide was added. The contents were stirred till dissolution and the brownish solution so obtained was filtered. To the filtrate an ethanolic solution of Mn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (0.058 g, 0.16 mmol) was added and stirred, when the solution turns intense brown. The contents were allowed to stir for 2 h when dark coloured precipitate separated out. It was then filtered, washed with 1 : 1 ethanol and dried in vacuum over fused CaCl₂ (yield 0.276 g, 64%) (Found : C, 48.15; H, 3.39; N, 12.17. Calcd. for C₅₆H₅₂N₁₂O₆Ru₂Mn : C, 48.47; H, 3.47; N, 12.11%).

[RuCl₂L¹]₂Mn(H₂O)₂ : Yield : 68% (Found : C, 46.68; H, 3.24; N, 12.50. Calcd. for C₅₂H₄₄N₁₂O₆Ru₂Mn : C, 46.89; H, 3.30; N, 12.62%).

X-Ray structure determination :

Single crystals of [Ru^{III}Cl₂L¹]₂Mn^{II}(H₂O)₂·H₂O·CH₂Cl₂ (0.32 × 0.28 × 0.36 mm) were grown by slow diffusion of hexane into its dichloromethane solution at room temperature. The unit cell parameters were determined by least-squares fit of 30 machine-centered reflections having 2θ in the range 15–30°. Data was collected at 293(2) K by ω-scan technique in the range 1.65 ≤ θ ≤ 22.55° on a Siemens R3m/V four-circle diffractometer

with graphite monochromated Mo-K_α radiations (λ = 0.71073 Å). Two check reflections measured after every 98, showed no significant intensity reduction. All data were corrected for Lorentz-Polarization effects. Out of 7458 reflections collected, there were 7321 unique of which 5936 reflections with I > 2σ(I) were used for structure solution. All the non-hydrogen atoms were made anisotropic (data-to-parameter = 7296/701). The structure was refined on F² by full matrix least squares using all unique data. Hydrogen atoms were added at calculated positions (riding model). All calculations were done on a 166 MHz IBM compatible PC/AT using the Siemens SHELXTL-VER.5.03³⁰ package. Data were deposited in CCDC under the deposit No. 791916.

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